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Far-Infrared Spectra of Copper(II) *n*-Alkanoates

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DESPITE the wealth of data¹⁻³ about copper(II) carboxylates, far-infrared studies of the metal ligand frequencies have, with the exception of some reports⁴⁻⁸, escaped attention. These workers assigned Cu-O stretching vibrations to copper(II) acetate complexes. Moreover, these studies lack a study of the copper-oxygen vibrations based on selection rules and a reasonable assignment could not be proposed. In the present communication, we have tried to include the selection rules to calculate the Cu-O (acetate) vibrations in different possible moieties, compared with the total number of vibrations actually observed and proposed a tentative assignment of Cu-O bands of some copper(II) *n*-alkanoates.

Experimental

Complexes were prepared by the literature routes⁹⁻¹². All the compounds were identified by elemental analysis as in Table 1.

Complexes	TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSIS OF THE COMPLEXES					
	Cu%		O%		H%	
	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
Cu(CH ₃ COO) ₂ ·H ₂ O	27.65	27.5	25.53	25.6	4.25	4.3
Cu(CH ₃ COO) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	31.83	31.7	24.06	24.4	4.01	4.18
Cu(CH ₃ COO) ₂	34.98	34.9	26.44	26.4	3.81	3.27
Cu(C ₂ H ₅ COO) ₂	30.34	30.3	34.36	34.2	4.77	4.7
Cu(<i>n</i> -C ₃ H ₇ COO) ₂	26.73	26.8	40.42	39.8	5.89	5.8
Cu(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ COO) ₂	19.04	20.0	57.57	57.65	4.19	4.2
Cu(C ₁₀ H ₇ CH ₂ COO) ₂	14.64	14.6	66.43	66.5	4.15	4.2

Far-infrared spectra were obtained as Nujol mulls between 500-200 cm⁻¹ on a Perkin-Elmer 377 spectrophotometer.

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Results and Discussion

Magnetic susceptibility, uv and visible spectral studies^{13,14} of copper(II) acetate, propionate, *n*-butyrate, phenylacetate and α -naphthylacetate show a dimeric bridged cage type of structure for these complexes, similar to that of copper(II) acetate monohydrate¹⁵.

In the structure of copper(II) acetate monohydrate the moiety immediately around the copper atom is CuO₅ in which the Cu atom is slightly above the plane of four oxygen atoms at the corners of a square base and the fifth oxygen atom is coordinated to the copper atom at *trans* axial position. The fifth oxygen atom is in principle, of different nature as shown in Fig. 1. The Cu atom is also linked to other Cu atom by a very weak δ -bond.

O* = Hydroxyl Oxygen.

Fig. 1. Dimeric structure of copper(II) acetate monohydrate.

No Cu-Cu bond has, therefore, been considered. The CuO₅ moiety belongs to the point group C_{4v}. For other anhydrous *n*-alkanoates the moiety is CuO₄ which also belongs to the C_{4v} point group. For CuO₄ moiety 2A₁+2B₁+B₂+2E normal vibrations are allowed of which only 2A₁+2E vibrations are active in infrared, whereas for the CuO₅ moiety 3A₁+2B₁+B₂+3E vibrations are allowed by the selection rules of which only 3A₁+3E are active in infrared. The presence of 4 and 6 bands in CuO₄ and CuO₅ moieties respectively lead us to conclude that the symmetry is not lowered.

If the Cu atom lie in the plane of the four oxygen atoms, the moiety CuO₄ has D_{4h} symmetry and will have 1A_{2u}+2E_u infrared active band from A_{1g}+B_{1g}+B_{2g}+A_{2u}+B_{2u}+2E_u vibrations allowed by selection rules.

Observed Cu-O bands and molecular structure: The total number of Cu-O bands observed are mentioned in Table 3. All vibrations due to ligands were neglected by comparing the spectra of copper(II) complexes with that of sodium salts of corresponding ligand. Vibrations due to lattice and crystal symmetry are not considered because these are very weak and mostly lie below 200 cm⁻¹. It has also been assumed that bending vibrations might be mixed with ring deformation due to existence of the ring in the structures.

The square pyramidal structure for CuO₅ moiety in copper(II) acetate monohydrate is well established¹⁵. Therefore, the CuO₄ moieties of anhydrous copper(II) *n*-alkanoates can be presumed to have square pyramidal structure which is supported

TABLE 3—OBSERVED M—O VIBRATIONS OF COMPLEXES

Compounds	$\nu_a(M-O)$ (cm^{-1})	$\nu_s(M-O^*)$ (cm^{-1})	$\nu_g(M-O)$ (cm^{-1})	Ring deform. + $\delta(O-M-O)$ (cm^{-1})	Ring deforma- tion	Ring+Torsion + $\delta(O-M-O)$ (cm^{-1})
Cr(CH ₃ COO) ₃ .H ₂ O	402s	375s	352sh	302vs	244 cm^{-1}	220m
Cu(CH ₃ COO) ₂ .H ₂ O	375bs	350m	333s	270s	240 cm^{-1}	235s
Cu(CH ₃ COO) ₂	380s	—	340bs	280vs	—	238s
Cu(CH ₃ -CH ₂ -COO) ₂	393s	—	318s	270m	—	251s
Cu(CH ₃ -CH ₂ -CH ₂ -COO) ₂	420s	—	310m	275m	—	245bs
Cu(C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ COO) ₂	425s	—	338m	285mb. mix	—	244s
Cu(C ₁₀ H ₇ CH ₂ COO) ₂	428s	—	230m	282sb. mix	—	260s

s=strong : m=medium : w=weak : vw=very weak : b=broad : sh=shoulder.

by their low magnetic moment values^{1,3,14} and our present spectral data (Table 3) on these complexes.

Assignment of bands : Stephenson *et al*¹⁶ made a coordinate analysis of BrF₅, which has square pyramidal structure in which apical fluorine atom is of different nature (different bond length). Our CuO₅ moiety of copper(II) acetate monohydrate is similar to BrF₅. Thus, on the similar ground the fundamental vibrations for CuO₅ moiety can be named as mentioned in Table 2. The vibrations of A₁ type are fully symmetrical but the E type of vibrations are degenerated and of asymmetric nature.

TABLE 2—FUNDAMENTAL VIBRATION OF CuO₅ MOIETY OF COPPER(II) ACETATE MONOHYDRATE AND ACTIVITY IN THE IR AND RAMAN SPECTRA

A ₁	B ₁	B ₂	E
Active in IR and Raman	Active in Raman	Active in Raman	Active in IR and Raman
$\nu_s(Cu-O^*)$	$\nu_{as}(Cu-O)$	$\delta_{as}(O-Cu-O)$	$\nu_d(Cu-O)$
$\nu_g(Cu-O)$	$\delta_{as}(O-Cu-O^*)$		$\nu_d(O-Cu-O^*)$
$\delta_s(O-Cu-O)$			$\delta_d(O-Cu-O)$

By changing the metal atom and comparing with the fir spectrum of Cr(CH₃COO)₃.H₂O, isostructural compounds¹⁷, we tried to justify the sequence thus established. Finally compromising assignments were made which fits for copper(II) acetate monohydrate and chromium acetate monohydrate. Similar assignments have been proposed for copper(II) *n*-alkanoates (anhydrous). The observed frequencies for these complexes have been presented in Table 3.

It is worth mentioning here that empirical band assignments are usually approximate since various vibrational couplings are neglected. The metal ligand vibrations can be identified with more accuracy by using the Laser Raman spectra in solid state with coloured lines and metal isotope techniques. In the lack of these the present assignments must be treated as tentative.

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